

HYDRIDES OF NICKEL

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A method for preparing nickel hydride in fairly large quantities has been described. It has been found that between 0° and 150° only two hydrides of nickel, NiH₂ and NiH, exist. Decomposition pressures of NiH₂ has been determined from room temperature to 150°. The heat of formation of NiH₂, calculated from the decomposition pressures, shows that it is of the same order of magnitude as those of the alkali and alkaline earth metals.

In a series of papers Weichselfelder and co-workers (Schlenk and Weichselfelder, *Ber.*, 1923, 56 B, 2030; Weichselfelder and Thiede, *Annalen*, 1926, 447, 64; Weichselfelder and Kossodo, *Ber.*, 1929, 62 B, 769) described the action of passing dry hydrogen into a solution of phenyl magnesium bromide in dry ether in which powdered anhydrous nickel chloride was suspended. They came to the conclusion that a hydride of nickel of the formula NiH₂ was formed according to the equation :

NiPh₂ is said to be formed as an intermediate product which decomposes into NiH₂ and C₆H₆ under the influence of hydrogen. According to Balandin, Erofeev, Pecherskaya and Stakhanova (*J. Gen. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1941, 11, 577), however, PhMgBr reduces nickel chloride to metallic nickel and the colloidal nickel thus formed absorbs hydrogen to form NiH, NiH₂ and NiH₃ depending upon the quantity of hydrogen taken up: $\text{NiCl}_2 + 2\text{PhMgBr} + 2\text{H}_2 = \text{NiH}_2 + \text{Ph}_2 + \text{MgBr}_2 + \text{MgCl}_2$. The present investigation was started with a view to finding out, if only one definite hydride or several hydrides were formed, and also the nature of these hydrides.

Weichselfelder and his collaborators (*loc. cit.*) obtained the hydride in minute quantities and carried out its analysis *in situ*. As it was intended to prepare larger quantities of the hydride the

FIG. 1.

apparatus shown in Fig. 1 was used. A was a round-bottomed flask with short neck. It was provided with a rubber bung, B, through which passed a glass stirrer, C, a dropping funnel, D, and inlet and outlet tubes, E and F, for hydrogen. Perfectly anhydrous and finely powdered nickel chloride was added to the dry ether in A and a stream of hydrogen, purified by passing through a mixture of dichromate and concentrated sulphuric acid, over heated copper and finally through concentrated sulphuric acid, was passed into the flask. The nickel chloride was constantly agitated by means of C. When all air had been displaced, the solution of freshly prepared PhMgBr in dry ether in D was run in. The phenyl magnesium bromide must be freshly prepared otherwise the reaction does not take place satisfactorily. For every gram of nickel chloride, 100 c.c. of dry ether were put into A and 50 c.c. of ethereal solution of PhMgBr containing 0.1 mol. of magnesium was used for the reaction. As soon as PhMgBr was introduced, the colour of the suspension began to change and finally it became black. The reaction was complete in 3 to 4 hours.

If nickel hydrides were merely adsorption compounds, as stated by the Russian workers, it was likely that compounds of different compositions would form when the preparation was made at different temperatures and hydrogen was passed for different periods. With a view to testing this

point, the preparations were carried out at, 0° , 15° and 25° by immersing the reaction flask in a suitable bath maintained at these temperatures and in some cases hydrogen was passed for a long time even after the reaction was complete. When the experiment was over, a small quantity of the substance was removed and its composition determined in the following manner. As the hydride is quantitatively decomposed into metallic nickel and hydrogen by water or alcohol, the small quantity of the substance taken out was introduced into a small flask fitted with a dropping funnel and a delivery tube, which was connected to a Hempel's burette. A measured volume of water-alcohol mixture was introduced through the dropping funnel and the evolved gas was collected in the burette. The decomposition occurred rapidly and the volume of hydrogen evolved was obtained by subtracting the volume of the liquid introduced from the total volume of gas collected. The nickel was then dissolved in the flask by adding dilute sulphuric acid and the nickel estimated in the solution as the nickel salt of dimethylglyoxime. It was found that volume of hydrogen evolved on the addition of acid was always equal to that given out on the addition of water. A large number of preparations was made at each temperature and the product obtained in each case was analysed and the results agreed quite closely. One typical result for each temperature is recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Temp. of preparation.	Wt. of Ni	Vol. of H_2 (N.T.P.)	Composition.
0°	0.1863 g.	69.0 c.c.	NiH_2
15°	0.4512	171.8	NiH_2
25°	0.2792	102.0	NiH_2

The decomposition pressures of the hydride were determined at different temperatures. For this purpose the hydride was repeatedly washed by decantation with dry ether and finally filtered through Allhin's apparatus in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The filtered substance was then dried by putting it in a test-tube through which a current of dry hydrogen was passed for some hours. The test-tube was kept immersed in a water-bath at 25° . The substance finally obtained was perfectly dry but still contained traces of magnesium salts as impurities. Measurements of decomposition pressures were repeated in four separate experiments with different samples of the hydride, and as the results were reproducible within 2 mm., it was clear that the presence of traces of impurities in the hydride did not vitiate the results to any great extent.

FIG. 2.

The all-glass apparatus used for measurements of pressure is shown in Fig. 2. The apparatus was so constructed that the volume of the apparatus from tap T_1 to tap T_2 , and the mercury level in the manometer M on the left-hand side is equal to that from tap T_2 to T_1 , and the mercury level in the manometer on the right-hand side. In order to test that the volumes on the

two sides were actually the same, the air inside the apparatus was completely displaced by pure and dry hydrogen which was introduced through T_1 and allowed to go out through the mercury trap C . The gas was passed for sometime with T_1 open and sometime with T_1 closed. When T_1 was closed the gas passed through M pushing up the mercury into the small bulbs above. When the apparatus had been filled with hydrogen, T_1 and T_2 were closed, and pressure of gas on the two limbs was equalised by opening T_4 which was then closed.

The apparatus was put into an electrically maintained air thermostat which could be kept constant to $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The thermostat was maintained at different temperatures and no change in the levels of mercury in M was noticeable indicating equal volumes.

For measurement of the decomposition pressures, a small quantity of dry nickel hydride, in a small weighing tube was introduced into B_1 , the whole apparatus from the three-way tap T_2 remaining filled with hydrogen. The air in B_1 was displaced by dry hydrogen which was introduced through T and allowed to escape through the other opening of T_2 . Gas pressure on the two sides was equalised through T_4 . The thermostat was set at definite temperatures, and at each temperature it was kept for sufficiently long time until equilibrium was attained. At each temperature the heights of mercury in the two arms of the manometer were read off by means of a cathetometer provided with a vertical scale and vernier. The difference between the heights gave the pressure at each temperature. The mean values of three different sets of experiments are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Temperature	29.8°	41.2°	51.2°	63.6°	70.2°	81°	89°	110.2°	130°	149.6°
Pressure (m. m.)	10.0	32.0	52.0	89.0	112.0	149.5	174.8	248.0	317.0	384.0

The above results are plotted in Fig. 3. It will be observed that it consists of two

straight lines which intersect sharply at one point indicating the presence of two solid phases. The point of intersection which occurs at 56° is the transition temperature of one form into the other. The change is irreversible, because it has been found that when the substance, which is formed at higher temperatures, is cooled to the room temperature in contact with hydrogen and left for 48 hours, hydrogen is not reabsorbed. The composition of the second solid phase has been determined by analysis. For this purpose the dihydride was heated to different temperatures from 70° to 150° and allowed to cool in contact with the evolved hydrogen, the ratios of hydrogen to nickel in the products were determined. The volume of hydrogen evolved when decomposed by the action of dilute sulphuric acid was collected and measured and the nickel in the solution was estimated by dimethyl glyoxime. The results obtained are tabulated below.

TABLE III

Temp. of bath.	Vol. of hydrogen at N. T. P.	Wt. of Ni.	Composition.
70°	22.6 c.c.	0.1110 g.	NiH
100°	27.2	0.1480	NiH
130°	26.3	0.1410	NiH
150°	25.7	0.1347	NiH

Nickel dihydride is a spongy, black substance which is fairly stable when kept under ether at temperatures below 0°. It decomposes rapidly in contact with moist air but in dry air the rate of decomposition is slow even at the ordinary temperature. It is decomposed quantitatively by water, alcohol or dilute acids; with the first two the decomposition is catalytic in nature resulting in the separation of metallic nickel and only two atoms of hydrogen are evolved per molecule of the hydride but with acids, the nickel salt of the acid is formed and four atoms of hydrogen are given out per molecule of the hydride. The formation of the hydride takes place mainly according to the equation given by Weichselfelder (*loc. cit.*) but it seems sometimes traces of diphenyl are also produced. Nickel monohydride has a slightly crystalline appearance, and is comparatively stable than the dihydride. It is completely decomposed by dilute acids. No evidence of the formation of NiH₄ has been found, although reactions were carried out at temperatures ranging from 0° to 25° and by passing hydrogen for varying lengths of time.

It is possible to calculate the heat of formation from the decomposition pressure-temperature data by means of the following thermodynamic relation, which is derived from the well known Clapeyron-Clausius equation,

$$\frac{d \log p}{dT} = \frac{Q}{RT^2} \text{ which, on integration, gives } Q = \frac{RT_1 T_2}{T_2 - T_1} \log \frac{p_2}{p_1}$$

where Q = heat of formation, $R = 1.9885$ cal. and p_1 and p_2 are the decomposition pressures at temperatures T_1 and T_2 respectively. The above equation can be used with exactness only at low pressures and small variations of temperature. While the importance of directly measured heat data is not denied, the calculated values are, no doubt, fair approximations to, or at least, capable of indicating the order of, the correct values. The heats of formations calculated in this manner are recorded in the following table.

TABLE IV

Temperature	Substance = NiH ₂			Substance = NiH.		
	35.5°	40.5°	46.2°	67°	75.6°	85°
Heat of formation (cal.)	19,330	15,060	9,971	8,261	6,472	4,968

The heat data recorded in literature are usually for a temperature of about 18°. The heat of formation Q_2 at temperature T_2 may be calculated from the equation

$$Q_2 = Q_1 + C_p (T_2 - T_1)$$

in which Q_1 is the heat of formation at temperature T_1 and C_p is the molecular heat capacity. The values of C_p for the hydrides NiH₂ and NiH are not known at any temperature. Over a small

range of temperature the values of C_p may be regarded as constant, so that if the heat data are plotted against the temperatures, straight lines are obtained. When these lines are extrapolated to 18°, the value of heat of formation of NiH_2 comes out as 35,200 cal. and that of NiH as 17,100 cal. The heat of formation of NiH_2 is thus comparable in magnitude with heat of the salt-like hydride BaH_2 for which the recorded value is 40,960. The high values of the heats of formation of the nickel hydrides suggest that there can be little distinction in the type of chemical binding in these compounds with that of the hydrides of alkali and alkaline earth metals. From the method of their preparation, there appears to be no analogy of nickel hydrides with such substances as the rare earth hydrides, nor is there any reason to suppose that these bear any relation with the products obtained when finely divided nickel absorbs hydrogen.

Further work on these type of compounds are in progress. In conclusion we wish to record our thanks to Dr. P. B. Ganguly and Mr. P. C. Sinha for their kind interest and ungrudging help.

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